

Kinetics of Oxidative Decarboxylation of Benzilic acid by *N*-Bromosaccharin

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Kinetics of oxidative decarboxylation of benzilic acid by *N*-bromosaccharin in binary solvent mixture of acetic acid-water in the presence of mercuric acetate has been investigated. The reaction is first order in oxidant and fractional order in substrate. Increase in $[H^+]$ increases the rate. Addition of sodium perchlorate, sodium sulphate and sodium acetate accelerates the rate whereas saccharin shows retarding effect. Activation parameters are evaluated and probable mechanism involving 1 : 1 complex formation is suggested.

OXIDATIVE decarboxylation of hydroxy acids by various *N*-haloimides have been studied¹⁻⁶. *N*-Bromosaccharin (NBSA), a new haloimide, has been employed in the oxidation⁷⁻⁹ and bromination¹⁰ of organic compounds. The present investigation deals with the oxidation of benzilic acid (BA) in acetic acid-water mixture in the presence of mercuric acetate by NBSA kinetically and a suitable mechanism is proposed.

Experimental

NBSA was prepared by brominating the alkaline solution of saccharin¹¹. Its solution was prepared in glacial acetic acid (G.R.) and was standardised iodometrically¹². The solution of benzilic acid (E. Merck) was prepared in glacial acetic acid. Other chemicals used were of standard grade.

The calculated volumes of reactants were mixed after attaining the desired temperature. The rate of reaction was followed from the aliquot portions of the reaction mixture taken at different intervals iodometrically.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of the reaction shows that one mole of benzilic acid is equivalent to one mole of NBSA. Under the experimental condition, the final products of oxidation were identified as benzophenone and saccharin.

Results and Discussion

Kinetic studies were arranged under the conditions $[BA]$ and $[Hg(OAc)_2] \gg [NBSA]$. All the investigations were made in the presence of mercuric acetate in order to avoid any possible bromine oxidation. Mercuric acetate acts as a scavenger for Br^- formed in the reaction and exists as $HgBr_2^{2-}$

and unionised $HgBr_2^{18}$ and thus ensuring only NBSA oxidation. Preliminary experiments were performed in the range $4.0-20.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ of $[Hg(OAc)_2]$. The plot of k_1 vs $[Hg(OAc)_2]$ shows that initially the reaction is first order dependence in mercuric acetate and then tends to limiting rate, i.e. zero order dependence at $[Hg(OAc)_2] = 10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Hence, all the studies were made at $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ mercuric acetate concentration.

The characteristic features of the oxidation can be summarised as follows. (i) Polymerisation test with acrylonitrile is negative ruling out the formation of free radical. (ii) On the five-fold variation of the concentration of NBSA, the first order rate constants for different initial concentration of NBSA at constant $[BA]$, $[Hg(OAc)_2]$ and $[HOAc]$ are obtained almost constant (Table 1) suggesting first order dependence in oxidant which is further evidenced from linear plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON NBSA AT 30°

[NBSA]	1.00	1.25	2.50	3.98	5.00
$10^3 M$	1.00	1.25	2.50	3.98	5.00
$10^3 k_1$ min^{-1}	4.87	4.34	4.40	4.44	4.36

The fractional order in benzilic acid was found from the slope ($=0.80$) of the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [BA]$ which may be due to the complex formation between BA and oxidant species as evidenced by a linear plot of k_1^{-1} vs $[BA]^{-1}$ with a positive intercept on y-axis (Fig. 1). (iii) The rate studies were made at different $[H^+]$ by taking H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ (Table 2). With increase in concentration of acid,

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Fig. 1. Plot of k_1^{-1} vs $[BA]^{-1}$; $[NBSA]=2.50 \times 10^{-3}$ M, $[Hg(OAc)_2]=1.00 \times 10^{-3}$ M, HOAc-H₂O=70% (v/v), temp.=80°.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON $[H^+]$ AT 30°

[Acid]	0.00	1.0	5.0	15.0	20.0	25.0	50.0
10 ³ M	0.00	1.0	5.0	15.0	20.0	25.0	50.0
A-10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	4.40	6.36	8.06	12.44	—	16.29	26.39
B-10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	4.40	6.23	10.37	23.92	31.06	45.15	—

A=H₂SO₄, B=HClO₄.

the rate of reaction increases indicating a participation of H⁺ ion in the mechanism. (iv) The effect of varying composition of binary solvent mixture of acetic acid-water on the rate of oxidation has been studied. It is noted that with increase in acetic acid reaction rate decreases. (v) Addition of saccharin retards the rate of oxidation (Table 3).

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [SACCHARIN] AT 30°

[Saccharin]	0.0	1.66	2.00	2.50	3.33	4.00
10 ³ M	0.0	1.66	2.00	2.50	3.33	4.00
10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	44.17	21.82	17.75	14.72	11.32	9.67

The plot between k_1^{-1} and [Saccharin] is obtained linear with positive intercept suggesting inverse dependence of rate on [Saccharin]. (vi) The effect of neutral salts like sodium sulphate, sodium acetate and sodium perchlorate enhance the rate of oxidation. (vii) The title oxidation was carried out at four different temperatures (30-45°) and activation parameters are obtained from the Arrhenius plot. The value of different parameters,

viz. E, A and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are 17.98 ± 0.78 kcal mol⁻¹, $11.87 \pm 0.99 \times 10^9$ s⁻¹ and -14.16 ± 4.92 e u., respectively. The value of energy of activation is more or less close to those obtained for other hydroxy acids^{14,15} and hence, it is supposed that above oxidation might follow a mechanism in which formation of reversible complex between the reactants is followed by the rate determining step involving C-C fission.

Mechanism: The reactive oxidant species of N-bromosaccharin in aqueous acetic acid are likely to be unprotonated NBSA, protonated NBSA, H₃O⁺Br, CH₃COO⁺HBr and molecular bromine, hence the oxidation may be a reaction between benzilic acid and any one of the above species.

The protonated species because of weakening of N-Br bond might solvolyse further to give H₃O⁺Br or its analogous acetyl derivative CH₃COO⁺HBr

The present investigation was carried out at 70% [HOAc] and with the decrease in [HOAc], enhancement of rate was observed which excludes the possibility of CH₃COO⁺HBr as oxidising species. Molecular bromine is also not likely to be reactive species as clean first order dependence on NBSA at all concentration was observed.

With increase in the concentration of H⁺ rate enhancement was observed both in H₂SO₄ and HClO₄. This favours the protonated NBSA as the reactive species in the present oxidation study. These observations lead to the mechanism,

The mechanism, thus involves one or more pre-equilibria for the formation of the oxidant species followed by a slow rate determining dissociation of complex formed between benzilic acid and Br⁺ to give the products. Applying equilibrium conditions for the formation of oxidant species k_{obs} is given as

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [BA] [H_3O^+]}{[Saccharin] \{1 + K_1 [H_3O^+]\} + K_1 K_2 [BA] [H_3O^+]} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{[Saccharin] \{1 + k_1 [H_3O^+]\}}{k K_1 K_2 [BA] [H_3O^+]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7)$$

The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[BA]$ or [Saccharin] are obtained linear with positive intercept on y-axis establishing the validity of step (6) and also it explains all the experimental results.

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